

PhD Proposal

Synthesis and fabrication of ZnO nanorods/GaN Heterojunction structure for Light-Emitting Diodes and photodetectors application

Abstract

1D ZnO nanostructures have excellent photoelectric features. Some of the properties include sub-wavelength, multiple light confinement, and ultrahigh intrinsic photoelectric gain. The Zinc Oxide nanostructures do not have grain boundaries, they have a higher phase purity, and long-distance order than the polycrystalline thin films. These properties make them suitable transport carriers for advanced optoelectronic devices. Some of the nanowires' properties include light emission, strong optical absorption, and photoconductive gains. These properties help advance solar cells (LED), nanogenerators, sensors, and field-effect transistors' performance. The world is pursuing the use of affordable white lighting LEDs in the global energy crisis. This paper attempts to offer insight on the development of heterojunction LEDs using Zinc Oxide nanotubes and nanorods on the p-type GaN with a NiO buffer layer insertion to enhance the emission of light.

Objectives of the study:

- i. Highlight the advantages and befitting features of Zinc Oxide use in nanotechnology
- ii. Demonstrate how to synthesize and fabricate ZnO nanorods/GaN Heterojunction structure for use in Light-Emitting Diodes and photodetectors
- iii. Present the equipment necessary for the above exercise.

Introduction

Zinc Oxide is a potential candidate for application in optoelectronics emitting blue to ultraviolet light. The compound bears fundamental advantages, including 3.37 eV wide bandgap, 60 meV considerable exciton binding energy, and 320 cm^{-1} room temperature high optical gain. The combination also has luminescent properties extensively researched for thin film, bulk, and nanostructure samples prepared through various methods and doped with various impurities.

One dimensional nanomaterial has small sizes that earn them unique optical, electrical, chemical, and mechanical properties. Their characteristics make them suitable for use in nanotechnology and nanoscience. Such features as multiple array light confinement and ultrahigh intrinsic photoelectric gain make one dimension Zinc Oxide an excellent material for nanotechnology. Several studies have studied materials made of Zinc Oxide for the construction of advanced optoelectronic devices, which have improved efficiency. One-dimensional Zinc Oxide nanomaterials' excellent properties earn it the potential for use as nano-structured systems basic unit. Nanostructures made developed from one-dimensional Zinc Oxide include nanowires, nanotubes, nanorods, and nanobelts (Tang, Li, and Zhou, 2016). The application requirements in these structures make one-dimensional Zinc Oxide ideal for use in providing an ideal medium in the construction of optoelectronic devices. The choice is because of such excellent properties as high mobility carrier transport, efficient confinement of light, and light emission. Thus, one dimension Zinc Oxide nanowires are used in devices used in the emission of light, photon detection, and sensing of biochemicals. The nanowire-like structures are also used in the physical studies investigating carrier transport, confinement of light, and loss of energy behaviors of one-dimension objects. Therefore, one-dimensional zinc oxide is favorable for low-dimensional

system basic phenomena extermination and construction of high performance and efficient nanodevices

Zinc oxide is an II-IV family member with features including 3.37 eV wide direct bandgap, 60 meV room temperature large exciton binding energy, and favorable properties for nanomaterial production. Zinc oxide materials can potentially be applied in optical waveguides, solid-state lighting, transparent conductive films, varistors, and gas sensors (Chen et al., 2019). The fact that zinc oxide has a wide bandgap means that it can be used in solid-state optoelectronic emitting in UV or blue spectral range, such as lasers. Besides, its feature of large exciton binding energy makes it an excellent candidate for use in displaying efficient room-temperature emission of excitons

LEDs made from ZnO and other related materials have received a lot of attention and have shown potential inherent in this material system (Sultan, Mumtaz, Ali, Khan and Iqbal, 2017). The LEDs are, and laser diodes developed from the application of ZnO nanomaterials and are considered cheap because of their affordable fabrication process and improved optical features. A few methods of fabrication are being explored in films and nanostructures of Zinc Oxide. Due to stable p-type Zinc Oxide insufficiency, heterojunctions are made with other existing p-type materials, such as SiC, Silicon, and Gallium Nitride. GaN is used in ZnO heterojunction fabrication for LED development since they have similar electronic features, crystalline wurtzite structure, and 1.8% lattice mismatch difference. The deep level emission of ZnO covers a wide visible spectrum range. White emission is obtained through a blue emission of GaN and deep level emission hybrid.

Literature Review

Tang, Li, and Zhou (2016) present several methods developed that one dimension the zinc oxide nanomaterials can be fabricated. These include vapor transport, electrodeposition, hydrothermal reaction, pulsed laser deposition, chemical vapor deposition, and molecular beam epitaxy. The researcher states that samples of Si, quartz, and sapphire can be obtained using these methods as each of them has their particular merits and weaknesses. The use of a gas vapor method to fabricate high-quality single-crystalline zinc oxide nanostructures requires high temperatures between 450-1000 degrees centigrade. The technique has such flaws as poor uniformity of samples, low product yield, and substrates' narrow choice. One dimension nanomaterials' preparation is done through solution processing due to their low cost, large-area manufacturing compatibility, and controllability. Zinc Oxide has superior optoelectronic attributes and environmentally friendly as compared to Galium Nitrite (Abbasi, Ibupoto, Hussain, Nur and Willander, 2018). Sarkar, Mahapatra and Basak (2018) contends that ZnO is considerably softer than GaN and is vulnerable to attacks by other chemicals and, therefore, less robust.

Chen et al. (2019) compared other nanomaterials with one dimension and argues that zinc oxide possesses three advantages, including the fact that it is a piezoelectric semiconductor for use in electric mechanical coupling inverters and sensors. It also has relatively high biosecurity and biocompatibility, making it suitable for use in medicine. Sun et al (2018) argues that biocompatibility of ZnO has let do its use in many tropical and oral medicines. One dimension Zinc oxide has the most extensive known nanostructure range, including nanotubes, nanobelts, nanotrees, nanoplates, nanorods, nanospheres, nanowires, nanoleaves, and nanosails. Others include zinc oxide tetrapods, porous array, microrod/microwire, matrix, and 3D network nanostructures, which have also been obtained. Presently, many researchers focus on

constructing devices based on zinc oxide nanomaterials, meaning that new tools are under development, including the room temperature lesser, photodetectors, light-emitting diodes, transistors, and sensors. This claim is supported by Jung, Kwon, Seo, Lee and Chuo (2017). The devices show high performance than other devices that use thin films and bulk materials due to the fact that they contain one dimension zinc oxide materials. The fact that these devices developed forms the use of one dimension zinc oxide nanomaterials shows that it has excellent potential for use in the application in many fields.

In an article, Huang et al. (2019) reviewed various zinc oxide nanostructures using solid vapor phase, nanoresonators, and field-effect transistors. Chen et al. (2019) examined the fabrication methods of fabricating and doping zinc oxide nanorods. They discussed the properties associated with them, such as luminescence, electron transport, field emission, and other applications. Huang et al, (2018) also reviewed the zinc oxide nanostructures fabricated using wet alloying, chemical methods and doping, patterned growth, catalysis, optoelectronics, sensing, and surface modification. The review looks mainly into the growth conditions of one-dimension zinc oxide nanostructures and the achievement of photodetectors and LEDs based on one dimension zinc oxide and the promising methods of improving these devices' performance.

Methodology

P-type GaN is commercially available and can be used to develop the present P-n heterojunction. A buffer layer of NiO is put in a sol-gel method before n-type ZnO nanorods are grown.

A nickel acetate sol-gel is prepared in 2-methoxy ethanol of 0.35M concentration. Di-ethanolamine added drop by drop as it is vigorously stirred at 60°C for two hours, and the nickel acetate to di-ethanolamine molar ratio kept constant at 1:1. A clean substrate of Gallium Nitride is spin-coated with the synthesized sol-gel 3 to 5 times to prepare the thin buffer layer of NiO deposition. The substrate is then annealed 20 minutes at the temperature of 180°C. The sample is then left in a 450°C preheated oven for a pure NiO phase. After NiO buffer layer deposition, the substrates are spin-coated twice or thrice with zinc acetate seed layer for Zinc Oxide nanorods growth and annealed for 20 minutes temperature of 120°C. The annealed substrates that now contain NiO buffer layer are then dipped vertically inside zinc nitrate hexahydrate and hexamethylenetetramine both of 0.0075 Molarity and left there for four to six hours at the temperature of 90°C. The nanotubes were obtained using chemical etching after the Zinc Oxide nanorods growth for 14 to 16 hours at 85°C using 5M Potassium Chloride.

SEM is then used to investigate the prepared sample morphology after nanotubes and nanorods' growth with or without the NiO buffer layer. The analysis of the composition of elements and the quality of crystals is using by the X-ray diffraction technique. The parameter semiconductor analyzer is used in heterojunction analysis. The prepared device luminescence was investigated by CL and EL studies.

Flow chart: Fabrication process of the isotype heterojunction UV photodetector

Equipment and chemical materials

- i. RF sputtering machine
- ii. Sol gel device
- iii. AFM
- iv. FESEM, EDX
- v. UV-VIS
- vi. XRD
- vii. Furnace
- viii. Photoluminescence
- ix. Electroluminescent
- x. XPS
- xi. TEM

References

- Abbasi, M.A., Ibupoto, Z.H., Hussain, M., Nur, O. and Willander, M., 2018. The fabrication of white light-emitting diodes using the n-ZnO/NiO/p-GaN heterojunction with enhanced luminescence. *Nanoscale research letters*, 8(1), pp.1-6.
- Chen, C.H., Chang, S.J., Chang, S.P., Li, M.J., Chen, I.C., Hsueh, T.J., and Hsu, C.L., 2019. Novel fabrication of UV photodetector based on ZnO nanowire/p-GaN heterojunction. *Chemical Physics Letters*, 476(1-3), pp.69-72.
- Huang, Y., Zhang, L., Wang, J., Chu, X., Zhang, D., Zhao, X., Li, X., Xin, L., Zhao, Y. and Zhao, F., 2019. Enhanced photoresponse of n-ZnO/p-GaN heterojunction ultraviolet photodetector with high-quality CsPbBr₃ films grown by pulse laser deposition. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, 802, pp.70-75.
- Sarkar, S., Mahapatra, A.D. and Basak, D., 2018. Self-powered highly enhanced broad wavelength (UV to visible) photoresponse of ZnO@ ZnO_{1-x}Sx@ ZnS core-shell heterostructures. *Journal of colloid and interface science*, 523, pp.245-253.
- Jung, B.O., Kwon, Y.H., Seo, D.J., Lee, D.S. and Cho, H.K., 2017. Ultraviolet light emitting diode based on p-NiO/n-ZnO nanowire heterojunction. *Journal of crystal growth*, 370, pp.314-318.
- Sultan, M., Mumtaz, S., Ali, A., Khan, M.Y. and Iqbal, T., 2017. Band alignment and optical response of facile grown NiO/ZnO nano-heterojunctions. *Superlattices and Microstructures*, 112, pp.210-217.
- Sun, J., Li, P., Gao, R., Lu, X., Li, C., Lang, Y., Zhang, X. and Bian, J., 2018. Piezo-phototronic effect enhanced photo-detector based on ZnO nano-arrays/NiO structure. *Applied Surface Science*, 427, pp.613-619.

Tang, X., Li, G., and Zhou, S., 2016. Ultraviolet electroluminescence of light-emitting diodes based on single n-ZnO/p-AlGa_N heterojunction nanowires. *Nano Letters*, 13(11), pp.5046-5050.